

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF RISK-BASED APPROACH IN SYSTEMATIC WELDING QUALITY ASSURANCE

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Abstract

The complexity and multifactorial nature of welding processes leads to rather high levels of potential for defects and associated risks. The analysis of the specifics of applying risks to welding processes allowed us to propose an approach to implementing continuous cyclical reduction of welding risks within the framework of a systematic approach to quality assurance.

Keywords: quality, welding, risk, Deming cycle, systems approach.

The more complex the production processes, the greater the possibility of deviations from the planned course of events and, as a result of such deviations, the possibility of failures, defects and other undesirable manifestations arises. The quality assurance system works to reduce the likelihood of such deviations [1].

Welding production is quite multifactorial, so the probability of failures associated with welding processes is quite high. This makes the application of risk control methods for welding processes even more important [2]. Analysis of systemic approaches to quality assurance in the context of the specifics of their application to welding processes allowed us to identify general trends in actions to limit welding risks [3].

The value of risk is determined by two main factors. First, risk is determined by the probability of the event that causes it. Usually, in welding quality assurance, such an event is considered to be the possible failure of a welded product, the appearance of a defect, failure to meet the established requirement for delivery conditions, and the like. Secondly, the risk is determined by the consequences of such an event. Welding processes are used, among other things, in the manufacture of potentially dangerous objects, such as pressure vessels, lifting and transport machines and mechanisms, technological equipment, pipelines, tanks [4]. The greater the potential hazard of the object to which welding processes are applied, the greater the potential risks associated with failures in these processes.

The Deming Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) cycle can be applied to any process, including welding. Each stage of the cycle has its own specific risk control for welding processes [5].

At the "Plan" stage, specifications for welded products and welding processes are developed and measures are developed to reduce the risks of non-compliance. Appropriate design of welded products establishes design solutions that minimize the potential consequences of failures in terms of impact on the environment, product users, and loss of functionality of welded products. When developing welding processes,

measures are provided to prevent the appearance of defects by using appropriate methods and parameters of the welding mode, welding materials, technological equipment, control of heat input and appropriate heat treatment of welded joints. An important method of preventing defects in the welding process is the attestation and certification of the welding process itself, the personnel employed, the welding materials used, and the equipment. A reliable means of reducing the probability of errors in design and technological solutions is the use of analogues, prototypes, and preliminary modeling. It is also important to be able to detect design and technological errors in a timely manner. This is achieved by conducting tests that precede the transfer of processes and products to production. As the effectiveness of timely detection of design and development errors decreases, tests can be placed in a series - resource tests, tests to failure, acceptance/rejection tests. Such tests are of particular value in a situation where they are conducted before the approval of design solutions and provide for prompt changes to the design based on the test results.

Significant opportunities for reducing welding risks are provided by the development and implementation of a control plan that accompanies the welding process, which allows for timely response to deviations in the welding process and welded products. The most effective way to reduce the risks of the welding process is to use automatic detection of failure causes (use of automated means of controlling welding mode parameters, sensors for tracking welded edges) with forced stopping of the welding process in the event of a critical deviation.

The second most effective step is to check the first part, which precedes the series of products at the established process settings. This approach is especially effective when using automated welding methods.

The third level of effectiveness in reducing risks by controlling the welding process is to identify the cause of defects by the operator on a quantitative basis,

that is, using measuring instruments (ammeters, voltmeters, pressure gauges, flow meters) to control the parameters of the welding mode and making the necessary adjustments to the parameters of the welding mode.

The fourth level of effectiveness is the detection of welding defects using automatic control, for example, penetration depth sensors. In this case, it is preferable to use sensors with automatic stopping of the welding process when a defect is detected.

The fifth step is the detection of a welding defect by an operator or defect inspector based on quantitative criteria using measuring equipment (flaw detector, caliper, hardness tester).

The sixth step of the rating is the detection of a welding defect by an operator or defect inspector by an alternative sign using templates.

The seventh step of the rating is the detection of a welding defect by an operator or defect inspector using organoleptic methods, that is, a visual method without the use of templates and measuring equipment.

Unsystematic random checks of welding process parameters or welded product are on the last eighth place in the ranking of approaches to reducing the risks of non-compliance through timely detection.

The acceptable level of risk was determined using the Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) method. The method is used to analyze the possibility and impact of design failures - structural solutions for a welded product (DFMEA) or directly the assembly and welding process (PFMEA). The risk is quantified by the risk priority number (RPN), the value of which varies in the range of 1...1000. Typically, a risk is considered acceptable if its Risk Priority Number (RPN) does not exceed 100. This applies to both DFMEA and PFMEA. Risk mitigation measures that aim to reduce the consequences, the possibility of failures, and their timely detection require additional resources. Therefore, at the "Plan" stage, the task of optimizing the costs of risk reduction is solved. The effectiveness and optimality of

the solutions found are determined at the Perform-Check-Act stages. These same stages ensure cyclical risk reduction.

The application of the proposed approach allows for the implementation of continuous cyclical reduction of welding risks within the framework of a systematic approach to quality assurance.

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